

Using metaverse to improve BIM processes

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Abstract

The technological rigidity that characterizes the Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Facility Management (AECO/FM) industry is the starting point for this academic work. Although Building Information Modeling/Management (BIM) is the start of something new, it should not be regarded as the end. There is a need for BIM to adapt, develop, and mature through integration with emerging technologies. Therefore, this research aims to investigate and identify the potential applications of the metaverse to improve BIM processes for design, information management and collaboration. Metaverse is a three-dimensional virtual world that combines digital technologies to produce data that is reliable, transparent, and traceable. To fully embrace connected construction, which is one of the main goals of Construction 4.0, it is thought that AEC/FM professionals should start communicating and collaborating in the metaverse, making it a new normal. Therefore, this study highlights the importance of metaverse and its use cases in various industries, particularly in the AEC/FM sector.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/iW7y61RRhZM>

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